

Review

The Adverse Influencing Factors to Programs and Policies on Education Access and Opportunities in Zimbabwe: A Literature Review

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Abstract: This paper is a qualitative study of the adverse influencing factors to programs and policies on education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe, based on literature review. The main push for this paper was the ever-changing world and the need to keep every learner abreast with the new learning trends that are continuously emerging in this global village while leaving no one behind. Also, the zeal to explore more about access and opportunities in education and to improve the education practices in Zimbabwe as well as to contribute to the body of knowledge for education access and opportunities justifies our choice for this topic. The guiding objectives for this paper were to analyze the programs on education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system, identify the adverse influencing factors to these programs and policies and recommend ways of improving education access and opportunities in the Zimbabwean education system. The paper, rooted in the Classical liberal theory, Postmodernism theory and Social Justice theory, looked into the application of these theories in different education systems. The paper further looked into the past programs and policies on education access and opportunities, the status quo of education access and opportunities and the researchers' perceptions about the future of education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe. As the paper adopted a qualitative approach based on literature review, secondary data sources were used to come up with conclusions and appropriate recommendations. The findings of this paper revealed that Zimbabwe education system still needs to improve access to education and opportunities as there are still a lot of school-going age children out of school. The study results also revealed that the government initiatives are being adversely influenced by the economic situation of the country, lack of social justice, lack of monitoring instruments and the continuous presence of corrupt officials in the system, encouraging unfair practices. The study then recommended the need for close follow-up on funds unveiled for educating the disadvantaged, weeding out of corrupt officials, comparative learning from other countries, timeous evaluation of policies and immediate modification. This paper further recommended marrying Zimbabwean characteristics to the education system and acknowledging Zimbabwe's uniqueness as a country.

Keywords: Education, Equity in Access, Equal Opportunities.

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Accepted: 31 December, 2023; **Published:** 3 January, 2024

How to cite this article: Chiremba Eunifer (2023). *The Adverse Influencing Factors to Programs and Policies on Education Access and Opportunities in Zimbabwe: A Literature Review*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(12), 93-104. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10452297>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Despite the government efforts, programs and policies to improve education access and opportunities, and the intervention of education partners in improving education practices, education access in Zimbabwe seems to succumb to a lot of unforeseen challenges. This paper is therefore going to focus on the adverse influencing factors to the success of policies and programs aimed at improving education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system and make necessary recommendation.

Definition of key terms

Education: is a conscious, deliberate effort to create a learning atmosphere and process to actively develop a learner's potential to have spiritual and religious strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed for themselves and society. (Wikipedia). While Aristotle views education as the process of training man to fulfill his aim by exercising all the faculties to the fullest extent as a member of society, for Socrates, education is the bringing out of the ideas of universal validity which are latent in the mind of every man. Similarly, John Dewey (1938), defines education as the continuous reconstruction of experiences (McDermott, 1981). Therefore, education is the learning process to actively develop the potential of the learner and the skills needed for themselves and the society.

Equity in Access: Equity in access to education is defined as the ability for all school going children to receive education from qualified personnel in dignified classrooms, with sufficient resources. (SETDA, 2021). For this particular study, education access is going to be defined as the chances available for school going populace in Zimbabwe to enrol, to remain in school, to complete their studies and the availability of resources for such.

Equal opportunities mean the laws and policies that promote fair and equal opportunities to all staff, children, and faculty irrespective of race, sex, and national origin (Miller, 2023). This study is going to define equal opportunities as the undiscriminating policies that are put in place to ensure that no one is left behind in the quest for education.

Background

Zimbabwe formerly known as Rhodesia, was under British colonial rule from 1890 to 1980 and inherited an education system whose access and opportunities were not for all but harbored policies that were discriminatory in nature and marginalized and disadvantaged the black majority. Rhodesia had explicit racial exploitation and education for the black population remained a privilege. (Chigwedere, 2014) Bottleneck screening was practised throughout the system, with fixed transition rates of blacks from primary to secondary schools a percentage of the primary school graduates was channelled to vocational secondary schools and the rest were just left to find their own way into the world.

After independence in 1980, many policies were formulated to address these imbalances and promote access to the education for all citizenry. The Government envisioned that education would eradicate ignorance thereby combating poverty and disease and unlocking political and socio-economic transformation. Adopting compensatory policies would rectify a lot of disparities and would ensure equal access and equity in the education system

Research objectives

1. To analyze policies and programs on education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system.
2. To identify the adverse influencing factors to programs and policies on education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system.
3. To recommend ways of improving education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system.

Research questions

1. What is the status quo of programs and policies on education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system?
2. Which factors are adversely influencing programs and policies on education access and opportunities in

Zimbabwe?

3. How best can education access and opportunities be improved in Zimbabwe?

Literature review

The classical liberal theory¹

The Classical liberal theory of equal access and opportunities advocated by Sherman and Wood propagates that each learner is born with some innate capabilities which cannot be substantively altered. This theory further endorses that it is the duty of the country/nation to provide an education system that is structured in a way that eradicates all the challenges that might hinder the nurturing of these innate capabilities. (Ngwacho, 2020) As education is regarded by many as a gateway to success, many learners from underprivileged communities or families use it as a catalyst to climb the social ladder. Thus, a country's education system should provide equal access to equitable and relevant education to all its citizenry and equal opportunities to all.

Postmodernism theory

Postmodernism theory is very significant in the study of access to education as it propounds that pluralistic multilingual is a way of accommodating linguistic dynamics which are prevalent in most countries around the world (Ngadini, 2016). Postmodernism is important in education systems as most learners will learn better, feel valued and accommodated when their language is used as a medium of instruction.

Social justice theory

Social justice means equal distribution of educational resources and equal treatment to make everyone feel physically and mentally safe and secure, at the same time feeling valued. This theory is highly related to ideas of fairness, equity and inclusion, and recognizes impact of power relations on both individual and society levels. (EducationHub, 2021). Pedagogies of social justice raise consciousness on feminism, multi-cultural education, emphasizing positive ethnic identity, social action and the zeal to address inequalities and injustice as propounded by Paulo Freire and John Dewey. (McDermott, 1981) According to (Sterns, 2022), schools can promote social justice either through formulation of policies that ensure equal distribution of resources and equity in education access for all learners or by being inclusive in teaching,, engaging all learners through multi-perspective approach to teaching, incorporating their experiences in the curricula and helping them understand their position in the larger community. Social justice is important in education as it gets to the root of the problems in schools and addresses inequalities both in the school and outside the school and builds stronger communities. (Sterns, 2022). Therefore, to promote access to education and educational opportunities, there is need to engage social justice discourse. Issues that need social justice include but not limited to gender inequality, racism, ethnicity and mistreatment.

Review of the past

Reforms in education to promote access.

The Free Education Policy (FEP) and Adult Literacy Campaign

Upon attainment of independence in 1980, the Government of Zimbabwe announced free and compulsory education in September of the same year. As a result of the Free Education Policy, primary school enrolment skyrocketed from 819 568 to 2 251 319 within the first eight years of independence (Mapako, 2012) The FEP was an attempt by the government to address disparities in the education system which discriminated against the black majority. Article 26 of the Declaration for Human Rights, made education a human right and stated that it shall be free, at least in the elementary stages. (Dekker, 1993) . FEP would then enable the formerly deprived majority to gain access to education and enhance equity in the education sector. (Chigwedere, 2014) , reiterated that churches actually pioneered the provision of education for the African people and now the government had to take over that responsibility. Zimbabwe Education Act of 1987 chapter 25:04 (8 June 1987) came into effect in order to legalise universal education and (Dekker, 1993)justify that, colonial education had a divisive and elitist effect hence the need

to work towards egalitarianism in independent Zimbabwe. However, during the implementation process, some challenges and obstacles emerged and although some temporary solutions were made, this alone could not fully address the education access and opportunities in the country.

Adult literacy campaign 1984, compensate those who skipped education during colonial era. (Mapako, 2012) This extension of learning time was very welcome during the early years of independence since there were a lot of cadres who had sacrificed their education for the freedom of the country and needed to catch-up with time lost during the liberation war.

Hot seating and gender equity in education

As a result of FEP there was a rapid expansion in the demand for education. The Ministry of Education, Sport, Arts and Culture in Zimbabwe opted for double session schooling to cater for the increase in demand for education at independence in 1980, (Towindo I. Sunday mail, 2012) This system was generally seen as a temporary measure when financial resources were constrained. However, the system that was supposed to be temporary has become a common feature in the schools due to rapid population growth as well many other economic challenges. It can still be argued that regardless of all the efforts to ensure equity in access to education, the system maintained the unequal distribution of education as some schools offered only one session while others were practising hot-seating. (Machingaidze T. P., 1998; Towindo I. Sunday mail, 2012) This is raising concern since it would mean that children who are receiving education are not at the same level in terms of resources and therefore performance might be affected. Furthermore, low performance at any educational level means that access and opportunities for the next level of education have been compromised.

The post-independence era also witnessed a lot of policies that aimed at eradicating gender inequalities in access to education and promote the girl child. (Chabaya, 2013). This move saw a lot of girls being enrolled in schools and women handling work posts that were predominantly male. Titles like "Headmaster" were replaced by "School head" to accommodate females and girls could also enrol for courses that were traditionally for boys.

Examination of minority languages and sign language

In a bid to improve access to education and education related opportunities for all, the Zimbabwe school examination council, ZIMSEC, has incorporated minority languages in the examination structure and learners can now choose the indigenous language most applicable to them with effect from November 2016 examinations. (ZIMSEC, 2016) This move was a welcome divergence from the traditional Chishona and IsiNdebele. Although some ethnic groups may feel left out, I believe this a positive step towards promotion of access to education for all as even Braille for the blind and Sign language are included for the examinations.

Reflections of the current

The status quo of education access

Access to education in a given system can be measured by the rate at which learners are being absorbed by the system at different educational levels. These key measures for this are: Apparent Intake Rate (AIR) and Net Intake Rate (NIR) at both Grade 1 and Form 1. By 2021, the primary school AIR was 93.38 percent while NIR for the same was 22.86 percent. During the same period, secondary school Apparent Intake Rate is 70.17 percent while Net Intake Rate is 21.01 percent. (EMIS, 2022). In this regard, it can be concluded that there is generally a high level of access to primary and secondary education in Zimbabwe. However, taking a closer look at the number of schools going population in Zimbabwe, Fig 1: School going age population by 2021 and those that are actually in school, the opposite becomes true.

Government initiatives to improve access

This section focuses on government initiatives, their intended goals and the situation currently on the ground.

Multi-cultural education

Zimbabwe is a multicultural, multi ethnic and multi-religion society and everyone has the right to participate in the cultural life of their choice. (Constituteproject.org, 2013) Thus, the education system has adopted a multi-faith approach in order to ensure everyone has access to education about these before they can make an informed choice. With 62% of Zimbabwean population being Christians, the education system might have taken a Christian Faith approach to religious studies, but the realization that cultural and religious beliefs influence behavior of individuals, communities and other groups, a multi-faith approach was adopted, resulting in Family Religion and Moral Education (FAREME) and Heritage studies in the school curriculum. These subjects give equal coverage to all religions and all ethnic groups' life styles and aim to improve access to education as all the learners have a chance to learn about and share their religion and culture in class.

Education and vocational training for refugees

Not only did the Zimbabwe government focus on its citizenry for education access, but also for refugees. By 2014, the primary school in Tongogara Refugee Camp had 1418 learners ranging from grades 1 to 7 while the secondary school had 375 learners. The secondary school, ends at ordinary level, but the advanced level students get full support of the refugee programme to study outside the camp. (UNHCR, 2014) Through this initiative, the refugees in Zimbabwe do not lose out on education or feel marginalized as they have access to formal education and a chance to better their future just like anyone else in the country.

Non formal education

The Non-Formal Education Policy (NFEP) is aimed at promoting alternative pathways to increase access to education and is a reflection of the government's commitment to increase access to education for all (MoPSE, Education Sector Strategic Plan 2016-2020, 2015) Non formal education facilitates the fulfilment of basic rights for all learners in line with the constitution of Zimbabwe which declared basic education a human right. The primary target groups for the NFEP are those Zimbabwean citizens that for one reason or the other did not get the chance to attend formal schooling and also those who did not fully gain from the opportunities they got for schooling and now need a second chance. The guiding principle for the NFEP is that every citizen has the right to access free basic education, including basic adult education to ensure that no one is left behind.

Non formal education (NFE) offers a variety of programmes that suit different individuals according to their personal needs. For those that never attended school, Basic literacy and numeracy is offered in all government primary schools across country, focusing only on English reading and Maths counting and recognition of numbers. Functional literacy is also offered in government primary school as a modification to basic literacy for those non formal learners that wish to go a step further in their education endeavors and equip learners with the skills for use in their day-to-day life situations like counting money, calculating change and other simple Mathematical operations. Communication skills are fostered at this stage and some learning areas besides English and Maths are introduced at this stage. Furthermore, NFE offers a Zimbabwe Basic Education Course (ZABEC) which caters for adults who missed primary school education but are willing to start afresh and get a primary school certificate. This course is offered within 3 years after which one can sit for a grade 7 examination together with the formal candidates. The first year, focuses on infant education, grade 1 to 2, the second-year grades 3-5 and the final year sees the learner getting grades 6 and 7 education and sit for the grade 7 national examinations after which they become certified primary school graduates. (MoPSE, 2015)

Apart from the primary schools, NFE programmes are also offered in secondary and tertiary education through Part Time Continuing Education (PTCE) and Open Distance Learning (ODL) respectively (MoPSE, 2015). PTCE offers classes after normal school hours either in the afternoon or in the evening to pursue secondary education whereas ODL is used in tertiary institutions for learners who are separated by time and distance and also learners socially and

economically disadvantaged. ODL does not respect any geographical boundaries and enrolment is open. Example of ODL practices is the Zimbabwe Open University, (ZOU) whose enrolment sours every year as many who cannot afford university accommodation fees and those who have to work and learn simultaneously through the institution in quest for knowledge. Other universities in the country also offer ODL courses through block release, weekend or holiday sessions without affecting the duration of the course.

Although non formal education is meant to promote equal access to education for all, the unavailability or rather unequal distribution of resources is derailing this government initiative as the supposed free education is never free and the learners are just too reluctant to pay for this kind of education and continue living in illiteracy. (MoPSE, 2015) , also acknowledges that the fees for participation, the reduced contact time, the need to have teachers with expertise and the need for changing roles for school managers are stumbling blocks in the implementation of NFE.

Basic education assistance module, (BEAM)

Basic Education Assistance Module, (BEAM) was launched in 2000 by the government in response to the worsening economic conditions as retrenchments and unemployment and increased poverty forced many learners out of schools for lack of school fees. (Maushe, 2019). The targeted beneficiaries for this module are orphans and vulnerable children, (OVC). The criteria for the selection of the beneficiaries include orphaned status, and health/social status of the household head. (EMIS, 2022).

National School Computerization Programme (NSCP)

The Presidential Computerization Program (PCP) was launched to ensure that a good number of Zimbabwean schools are equipped with ICTs to enhance teaching and learning activities, thereby preparing the learners for the future. (Shumba, 2014)..Although this initiative was welcome in urban schools, these computers became a liability in the rural schools as most of the schools had neither the electricity nor the computer labs for these computers (Shoorai Konyana and Elias, 2013) . In some cases, classrooms had to be converted to labs and due to lack of infrastructural costs, other schools just packed the computers away as electricity was out of reach for many. In other words, promotion of access failed to reach maturity stage as poor schools could not be part of the implementation process.

Broadcasting lessons

As a catch-up strategy to time lost during COVID 19, the education partner, UNICEF produced 40 TV and 1000 radio lessons targeting 1.7 million learners and a further 79,560 through the learning passport. (Oyewale, 2022) . Other on-line learning platforms like, the Econet's Ruzivo digital learning and Wagona Maths, a Mathematics tutorial platform have emerged with the aim of enhancing ICT integration to the learning process. (Zambaza, 2022) These platforms, however, require a computer or a smart phone and internet connectivity in order to access the learning material. The introduction of the learning platforms is a noble idea to compliment ICT integration, but with less than 25% of the schools having internet connectivity, (EMIS, 2022) (MOPSE, 2022) it is a far-fetched dream for many. On this note, disadvantaged learners are being deliberately excluded by the system from partaking in ICT integration in their learning experiences. Without a radio or television as the case with most rural homes in Zimbabwe, and a smart-phone, one cannot access the on-line lessons, even though they have been "made available". Thus, during the COVID 19 lock down, while the advantaged learners were advancing their education, the poor were running the streets and bushes in search for food and the education access gap was widening between the two social camps.

Zimbabwe is still struggling with equity in education access and opportunities despite all the efforts that were made. The next part will discuss the adverse influencing factors to these policies

The adverse influencing factors to policies on education access and opportunities.

The literature reviewed brought to light some adverse influencing factors to education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe as follows:

Language barriers

Although Zimbabwe recognizes 16 languages including sign language, some ethnic dialects and languages were left out of consideration due to the ‘Insignificant number’ of the people who speak those dialects. Example of such are the Chewa people in most mining towns, the San in Tsholotsho rural district, the Fengu in Ntabazinduna, the Tonga along the Zambezi valley and the Xhosa people in the southern parts of Kezi district. The official language in Zimbabwe is English but the language of instruction in schools especially primary schools is adopted from the main ethnic groups in the province. For example, in Mashonaland province, Chishona is used, in Matabeleland, IsiNdebele is used, in Manicaland, ChiManyika and so on. This interprets to barriers to access to education as children from minority ethnic groups who are not fluent or skilled in those languages have their performances invariably affected as they can neither interact with the teacher nor other classmates (Keith Phiri a, 2020) and feeling excluded, they consequently drop out of school.

Poverty, ethnicities and cultural influences

A study that examined opportunities and access to formal education for the San community in the rural district of Tsholotsho in Zimbabwe revealed that the learners from this ethnic group have a lot of challenges ranging from abject poverty, long distances travelled to schools, dilapidated infrastructure, existing stereotypes to negative attitudes towards schooling itself. (Keith Phiri a, 2020). The San people, being originally hunters and gatherers, they usually practise hand-to-mouth way of life. Thus, going to school and bringing nothing home at the end of the day is regarded mainly as a sheer worst of time. The perceived negative attitude towards education has had telling effects on the marginalized San community and the hindrances to attaining formal education has earned them names like “separatists”, “non-conformist” and at worst “primitive” in as far as participating in modern and mainstream development is concerned. (Keith Phiri a, 2020)

Demographic issues

population dynamics have a great influence on education access as the number of schools built in a given area is directly proportional to the total population of school going ages in that particular area (Koffi, 2021). As simulation models are used for projections to adjust school Organisation visa vie the local school age population, remote and marginalized communities tend to suffer most as their population is too low to attract more schools, yet the distance the children have to walk to school will end up excluding them from the schooling system. Evidence gathered in Tsholotsho, a remote district of Zimbabwe showed that all the respondents agreed that distance from school was indeed a barrier to education access for the San community. (Keith Phiri a, 2020)

(Moyo, 2022), lamented the shortage of basic services like water, roads, electricity and internet access among others in rural schools in Zimbabwe. A widening technological divide between rural and urban schools in Zimbabwe is evident in that urban schools are moving at par with the fourth revolution while the rural schools are still to catch-up with the second revolution of technology(Moyo, 2022). It is therefore imperative for the country’s educational system stakeholders to put heads together and find solutions and strategies that can bridge this technology divide, while improving access to educational resources and opportunities to the learners in the rural schools.

Unfair practices in the education system

Zvobgo (1994:) emphasized that, corruption, nepotism, political, lack of imagination on the part of policy makers, wrong social programmes and priorities have resulted in serious misallocation and misuse of resources. The BEAM funding is administered by the social dimension fund, (SDF), in the Ministry of Public Service, Labour and Social Welfare, but selection is done in schools and a lot of corrupt activities render this initiative fruitless as the targeted beneficiaries do not end up receiving the assistance and are left out. Table 1: The number of OVCs assisted through BEAM in 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

For example, in 2021 not all the OVCs were able to receive BEAM assistance at ECD and Secondary levels while some 14937 primary school learners who are not OVCs, benefited from this funding. (EMIS, 2022) The number of OVCs assisted through BEAM in 2021 (EMIS, 2022) Interpreted, this means that there are some unfair practices that are ongoing in the education sector that derail the government efforts to promote equal access to education, an issue that needs to be looked into.

These challenges and others yet to be established, impinged the success of the Free Education Policy in Zimbabwe, affecting BEAM and will always derail government efforts in improving access to education if left unattended.

Suggested strategies to improve education access and opportunities

Prioritizing education in the national budget

To date, the Zimbabwean government is in the process of a curriculum review consultation which might extend education access and opportunities to all. With the government having committed itself to transform education through recognizing it as a fundamental human right and a base for other human rights, (Munangagwa E, 2022)i, this can improve access to education and educational opportunities in Zimbabwe.

As follow-up to the Zimbabwean President's commitment that he made during the UN General Assembly in New York on 22 September 2022, MoPSE, has started preparations for the curriculum review consultations which is a sign that the government is now willing to involve the stakeholders in the planning and shaping of the curriculum which hopefully might instil a sense of ownership and further improve access to education. (Thabela, 2023), emphasizes the need to address the issue of exclusion, renewal of curricula and pedagogies as well as promoting equitable learning through steering digital transformation. It is the researcher's hope that these consultations will address the issue of education access and opportunities, eradicating the rural disadvantages and promoting social justice.

Adopting national characteristics into the education system.

According to research, the meaning of the Ministry Of Education, (MOE) is based on China's own features, that is living harmoniously. With 56 ethnic nationalities, 55 ethnic minorities, 293 different languages, 126 spoken languages and around 30 written languages, still, China managed to design policies that improved equal access to education for all. (Chen, 2023). Special bureaus and special funds for the education of learners who come from marginalized communities were some of the strategies employed to improve education access and opportunities in China.. Moreover, the government makes a thorough should follow-up and monitor systems for whatever funds it releases to ensure that the targeted beneficiaries are the ones that benefit and avoid gate crushers like what happened in Shanghai with the Left –behind children's case (Chen, 2023).

Paradigm shift

As suggested by (Keith Phiri a, 2020) there is need for the government, the developing agents and actors in policy to have a paradigm shift in attitude and behaviour so that there is no community or ethnic group that is regarded as a nuisance, but rather try to make everyone feel valued and incorporated in the learning process. To address inequalities in education access and opportunities, educators might also try to urge the learners to have action projects in which they engage in social discourse both in and outside school. (Sterns, 2022) . These kinds of activities help getting learners involved in their own communities and learn more through interactions, thereby instilling a sense of belonging, being valued and the will to keep on learning.

As this section has reviewed the related literature and identified the research gap, the next part of the paper will unveil the methodology adopted for this paper.

Research gap

A lot of studies have been done pertaining external barriers to education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe but there is lack of research on the barriers to policies and programs aimed at increasing access and opportunities.

Research Methodology

This paper is adopting a qualitative approach based on literature review. Thus, the paper focuses on analyzing the existing researches on education access and opportunities and drawing conclusions based on the analysis. For this research, journal articles, books, reports, and ministry policy documents and circulars were used as the sources of data. To ensure that the literature used for this research is relevant, the researcher used keywords to search for literature on Google and also looked at reference lists from existing literature in order to identify more data sources. In addition, the paper made use of experts in the area of education access to gain more insight of the topic.

Findings

The reviewed literature has shown that Zimbabwean education system still has a long way to go in order to improve access to education and opportunities to learners, as most school-going age children are still out of school. The government initiatives to improve access to education have over the years been adversely influenced by the economic situation of the country, lack of social justice, lack of monitoring instruments and also the continuous presence of corrupt officials in the system, encouraging unfair practices.

Conclusion and recommendations

This paper discussed the theories and principles of education access and opportunities, the past, the present status quo of education access and opportunities in Zimbabwe education system. Furthermore, the paper analyzed the government efforts to promote education access and opportunities, the factors that are affecting equity in access and offered some recommendations on how to improve education access and opportunities in the Zimbabwe education system. The paper therefore makes the following recommendations to the Government of Zimbabwe (GoZ), through MoPSE

1. Need to follow up on specific funds unveiled for educating the disadvantaged as this will help to ensure that only the targeted beneficiaries are actually benefiting and there are no malpractices.
2. Weed out corrupt officials from the education system as they derail government efforts by channeling the resources to their own advantage.
3. Comparative learning from other countries.
4. Timely evaluation of policies and immediate modification.
5. Marry Zimbabwean characteristics to the education system acknowledge Zimbabwe’s uniqueness as a country.

The number of registered OVCs for the year 2021

LEVEL	MALES	FEMALES	TOTAL
ECD	60977(18.56%)	59737(18.29%)	120714(18.43%)
Primary	304241(20.98%)	304178(20.99%)	608419(20.99%)
Secondary	140589(26.13%)	149258(27.15%)	289847(26.65%)
Total	505807	513173	1018980

Table 1: number of registered OVCs by 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

Table 2

The number of OVCs assisted through BEAM in 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

Level	No/ of OVCs	No/ assisted	Variation
ECD	120714	53 159	67555

Primary	608419	623 356	-14937
Secondary	289847	182 477	103370
Total	1018980	858992	155988

Table 2: number of assisted OVCs by 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

Fig. 1: School going age population by 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

Fig. 2: Number of learners in school by 2021 (EMIS, 2022)

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgements: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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